

The assessment of quality attributes for biosimilars: a statistical perspective on current practice and a proposal

[Short title: The assessment of quality attributes]

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Establishing comparability of the originator and its biosimilar at the structural and functional level, by analyzing so-called quality attributes, is an important step in biosimilar development. The statistical assessment of quality attributes is currently in the focus of attention because both the FDA and the EMA are working on regulatory documents for advising companies on the use of statistical approaches for strengthening their comparability claim. In this paper, we first discuss "comparable" and "not comparable" settings and propose a shift away from the usual comparison of the mean values: we argue that two products can be considered comparable if the range of the originator fully covers the range of the biosimilar. We then introduce a novel statistical testing procedure (the "tail-test") which is compatible with the proposed understanding of comparability and compare the operating characteristics of the proposed approach with approaches currently used in practice. We demonstrate that currently used approaches cannot be recommended without restrictions because the approaches either cannot correctly identify comparable settings and/or have operating characteristics which highly depend on the sample size. In contrast, our proposed methodology is compatible with the proposed understanding of comparability and has, compared to other frequently applied range-based approaches, the advantage of being a formal statistical testing procedure which controls the patient's risk and has reasonable large-sample properties.

1 Introduction

2 Biologics are large molecule drugs that have brought life-changing improvements to the
3 health of patients in many important disease areas. A biosimilar (the test product) is devel-
4 oped and approved as a comparable version of an already marketed biologic (the originator
5 or the reference product) and can be sold after the patent or other statutory exclusivity
6 period of the originator has expired [1]. For the showing of biosimilarity, regulators rec-
7 ommend a step-wise approach. The establishing of comparability at the quality/analytical
8 level, i.e., demonstrating the similarity of the biosimilar and the originator at the structural
9 and functional level, is generally seen as the first and most important step for the approval
10 of biosimilars [2]. The use of statistics in the comparability exercise of quality attributes
11 is currently in the focus of attention because both the EMA and the FDA are working on
12 regulatory guidances on this topic. However, there is still an ongoing controversial discus-
13 sion on the question of if and how statistical approaches can be used for supporting the
14 comparability claim. This is evident by the fact that the FDA has withdrawn its published
15 draft guidance on this topic after reviewing the received comments [3].

16

17 We note that analytical studies are also the main piece of evidence for demonstrating
18 comparable product quality after a manufacturing change. The main differences between
19 the two types of assessment lies in the amount of available data and in the magnitude of
20 the change. We focus on biosimilars in this paper, but our conclusions may also be relevant
21 for manufacturing changes.

22

23 In this paper, we discuss several quantitative methodologies for performing a compara-
24 bility assessment from a statistical perspective. This papers builds on the work of [4] and
25 [5] who proposed and studied statistical methodologies for analytical similarity assessment
26 using a null and alternative hypothesis which is based on equivalence of the mean value.
27 However, in this paper, we first take a step back and critically discuss which situations
28 should be considered as "comparable" and which situations should be considered as "not
29 comparable". This is motivated by observations made during biosimilar development in
30 practice [6, 7, 8] and by the relevant ICH guidelines which request that the quality attributes

31 are controlled to be within limits (one-sided, e.g., for impurities) or ranges (two-sided) and
32 not in terms of mean values. A first proposal along those lines was made by [9, 10], but
33 their proposed approach contained also a mean value constraint and was therefore not fully
34 focussed on the range. In addition, it was not introduced as a formal inferential testing
35 procedure. The aims of this paper are twofold: on the one hand, we aim to illustrate the
36 inappropriateness of currently available statistical methodology for quality assessments if
37 *our* understanding of comparability is used. On the other hand, we aim to present a more
38 suitable alternative approach: we introduce the so-called tail-test which is an inferential
39 methodology for comparability claims which is compatible with the ICH guidelines in the
40 sense that a range-type hypothesis is tested. The operating characteristics of the tail-test
41 are compared to the other approaches which are currently discussed.

42 **Material and Methods**

43 In this section, we first introduce our understanding of "comparable" and "not compara-
44 ble" settings. Afterwards, we present our proposal for an inferential statistical approach
45 (the so-called tail-test) for quality assessment which is in line with the aforementioned
46 definition of comparability. Next, we list the selected statistical methodologies which are
47 most often used in practice for establishing comparability. These approaches are compared
48 to the tail-test in a simulation study whose settings are described in the last part of this
49 section.

50

51 Let X_R and X_T be random variables that represent the measurement of the quality
52 attribute of Reference and Test, respectively. In this paper, we assume that both sets of
53 random variables follow a normal distribution with mean μ_R and standard deviation σ_R
54 for Reference and μ_T and standard deviation σ_T for Test. All observations are assumed
55 to be independent and identically distributed. It should be emphasized that these as-
56 sumptions might not be valid in practice for all quality attributes. However, these are the
57 typical assumptions for many statistical approaches and that is why we have decided to
58 use this simplified scenario. Let x_1, \dots, x_n be the realizations of X_T and y_1, \dots, y_m be the
59 realizations of X_R .

60 **A meaningful characteristic of interest for the comparability as-**
61 **essment of quality attributes**

62 When two populations are compared, the focus is typically on comparing the locations of
63 the two populations, which are given, for example, by the mean values. Then, two popu-
64 lations would be considered "comparable" if the difference in their expected mean values
65 is "small". This is also what is proposed explicitly by Tsong et al. [4] and in the with-
66 drawn FDA's draft guidance [3] on statistical approaches for comparability in biosimilar
67 development for the most critical quality attributes. In the EMA draft reflection paper on
68 comparability assessment of quality attributes [11], the mean value is also a frequently used
69 example for the characteristic of interest. However, in routine manufacturing, the mean
70 value of observations for quality attributes across lots of the Test or Reference material is
71 of no relevance for defining acceptable quality. The ICH Q8 guideline [12], for example,
72 requests that "a CQA [critical quality attribute] is a physical, chemical, biological, or mi-
73 crobiological property or characteristic that should be within an appropriate limit, range,
74 or distribution [e.g., a particle size distribution for solids] to ensure the desired product
75 quality".

76

77 The shift from the mean value as the characteristic of interest to a range-type point
78 of view is also motivated from experience in practice in biosimilar development: since
79 comparability according to the ICH guidelines is currently only defined in terms of limits
80 or ranges, it is not guaranteed that the mean value of the reference product is constant
81 over time. Therefore, even the reference product might not fulfill a comparability criterion
82 based on the mean value if different manufacturing time frames are compared. Using the
83 mean value as the characteristic of interest for the comparability exercise of the biosimilar
84 can be seen as an uncontrollable risk for the developer of the biosimilar and we illustrate
85 this in Figure 1 (left hand panel): a biosimilar developer might develop its production
86 process so that the mean values are comparable to the reference product lots which are
87 available at the start of the biosimilar development (mean values of Test and Reference are
88 identical in the beginning in Figure 1, left hand panel). Afterwards, the reference product
89 may undergo manufacturing changes and, while still being within specification limits [13]

90 that were agreed with the regulatory authorities, the mean value might shift downwards
91 (starting from time $t = 21$ in Figure 1). If the biosimilar developer compares the mean
92 value of the proposed biosimilar to the mean value of the reference product at a point in
93 time after the manufacturing change, the mean values might not agree and lead to the false
94 conclusion that the biosimilar and the reference product are not comparable - even though
95 the biosimilar was comparable to the reference product at the time the development of the
96 biosimilar started.

97 *Please place Figure 1 about here.*

98 This is indicated in the left panel of Figure 1 by the solid lines which gives the cumula-
99 tive mean values for Test and Reference: while both lines are at a comparable level at the
100 beginning (e.g., at $t = 10$), the cumulative mean value of Reference is shifting downwards
101 indicating a clear separation of the mean values at time $t = 40$. Therefore, a test on equiv-
102 alence of mean values for all observations until $t = 40$ would, most likely and depending on
103 the pre-defined equivalence margin, not allow a claim of comparability. On the other hand,
104 if we focus on the distributions themselves (right hand panel in Figure 1), it is clear that
105 the range of Reference completely covers the range of Test and therefore the two products
106 would be considered equivalent if a range-type criterion would be applied. It is important
107 to note that shifts in the mean value are not only of theoretical interest, but this pattern
108 has already been observed in practice and reported in publications [6, 7, 8].

We emphasize that comparing the empirical distribution functions instead of the mean values of Test and Reference, for example with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test [14], is not appropriate in this situation, since a smaller variability of Test than of Reference is acceptable (see, for example, ICH Q10, [15]). That is why, in this paper, we focus on a range-type hypothesis: we consider two products to be comparable if the tails of the distribution of Test are, at most, "slightly" heavier than the tails of Reference, whereupon "slightly" is more concretely defined via the equivalence margin c (see below). For that, let R_x be the $x\%$ -quantile of the Reference product, i.e., the value such that $x\%$ of the probability distribution of Reference lies below it. Then, we test the null hypothesis:

$$H_0 : 2q - ((P(X_T < R_q)) + P(X_T > R_{1-q})) < c, \quad (1)$$

versus the alternative hypothesis:

$$H_1 : 2q - ((P(X_T < R_q)) + P(X_T > R_{1-q})) \geq c,$$

109 where c is the equivalence margin (chosen, in discussion with subject matter experts,
110 to be appropriate for the quality attribute used in the comparison) and q is the considered
111 quantile with $q \in [0, 0.5]$ which has to pre-specified. Reasonable choices are, for example,
112 $q = 0.05$ or $q = 0.1$. Figure 2 provides an aid to understanding the logic behind these
113 hypotheses.

114

115 In Figure 2, the quantiles R_q and R_{1-q} are taken from the distribution of Reference
116 (left hand panel, dotted lines). Then, the probability mass of the distribution of Test
117 which is outside of the identified quantiles is calculated, i.e., the probability of observing a
118 value of Test which is even more extreme than the estimated quantile of Reference (colored
119 parts in the right hand panel, denoted by $C_l := P(X_T < R_q)$ for the red area and by
120 $C_u := P(X_T > R_{1-q})$ for the blue area). We consider the total probability to observe a
121 value of Test outside of the quantiles of Reference, i.e., we focus on the sum of C_l and C_u
122 and compare this to $2q$ (which is, by construction, the probability that a value of Reference
123 is more extreme than the quantiles R_q and R_{1-q} , respectively).

124

Please place Figure 2 about here.

125 If the tails of Reference are much heavier than the tails of Test, then the sum of the
126 area of the colored parts is much smaller than $2q$. Thus, for claiming comparability, it is
127 required that the difference between $2q$ and the sum of C_l and C_u is *large*. The value c
128 gives the equivalence margin: one could set this value to $c = 0$ which means that we test
129 if the sum of the probability mass below the q -quantile and above the $(1 - q)$ -quantile of
130 Reference is larger for Reference than for Test (i.e., "full" comparability). However, in the
131 context of equivalence and non-inferiority testing, one generally allows for a margin in the
132 size of a difference which reflects the amount that one would not consider two products
133 to be different from a clinical point of view [16]. For example, in the approach proposed
134 by Tsong et al. [4], a difference in the mean value of $1.5\sigma_R$ is proposed as the equivalence
135 margin. Therefore, in order to stay aligned with current practice, we allow that the tails

136 of Test can be *slightly* heavier than the tails of Reference and still claim equivalence. The
 137 acceptable difference is given by the pre-specified constant c which has to be chosen in
 138 discussion with subject matter experts.

139 **The tail-test**

140 The test statistic, which we introduce in this section, uses the condition stated in Equation
 141 (1) as the null hypothesis and therefore considers the probability that a more extreme
 142 value for Test than the chosen q - and $(1 - q)$ -quantiles of Reference is observed. We refer
 143 to the proposed approach as the *tail-test*. The tail-test assumes normally distributed and
 144 independent data. However, the general idea of the approach can easily be adjusted to
 145 allow for other types of distribution, e.g., for a mixture distribution in which potential
 146 manufacturing changes are incorporated as long as sufficient data are provided for allowing
 147 a reliable estimation of the parameters of the distribution. It may, in principle, also be
 148 possible to take into account information on the lot structure of the data which can be
 149 useful if substantial lot-to-lot variability is expected. This is also discussed by the FDA
 150 [3]. The tail-test follows the following procedure:

- 151 1. Estimate separately the mean value and variance of Test T and Reference R, assuming
 152 normal distributions $(\hat{\mu}_R, \hat{\mu}_T, \hat{\sigma}_R^2, \hat{\sigma}_T^2)$.
2. Calculate the q and $(1 - q)$ -quantiles of Reference using the fitted normal distribution
 from step 1, i.e., the quantiles are given by

$$\hat{R}_q = \hat{\mu}_R + z_q \cdot \hat{\sigma}_R \text{ and } \hat{R}_{1-q} = \hat{\mu}_R + z_{1-q} \cdot \hat{\sigma}_R,$$

153 where z_q is the q -quantile of the standard normal distribution, e.g., for $q = 0.05$,
 154 $z_{1-q} = 1.96$.

3. Calculate the probability that, assuming the fitted normal distribution of T, an ob-
 servation of T is observed that is smaller than the lower quantile \hat{R}_q or larger than
 the upper quantile \hat{R}_{1-q} . For that, let $X_{T,e}$ be a normally distributed random variable
 with mean value $\hat{\mu}_T$ and standard deviation $\hat{\sigma}_T$. Then, these probabilities are

$$\hat{C}_l := P(X_{T,e} \leq \hat{R}_q) \text{ and } \hat{C}_u := P(X_{T,e} \geq \hat{R}_{1-q}).$$

4. The difference between $2q$ and the sum of \hat{C}_l and \hat{C}_u serves as the test statistic w which is a realization of a random variable W , i.e.,

$$w = 2q - (\hat{C}_l + \hat{C}_u).$$

155 The realization of the test statistic is compared to the $(1 - \alpha)$ -quantile of the distribu-
 156 tion of W under the null hypothesis. If the observed value w is larger than this critical
 157 value, comparability can be claimed. The derivation of the theoretical distribution un-
 158 der the null hypothesis is mathematically challenging and we therefore use critical values
 159 $W(\alpha, c, q, m, n)$ which are obtained using simulation. A Shiny-App [17] is available at
 160 <https://nballarini.shinyapps.io/tailTest/> which gives a graphical interface for cal-
 161 culating the test decision with the tail-test for real datasets. For readers who prefer an
 162 implementation in R [18], we also provide code as supplementary material on the publisher's
 163 webpage.

Numerical example: We set $q = 0.1$, choose a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and an equivalence margin of $c = -0.1$. We then assume that $n = 20$ measurements of Test and $m = 20$ measurements of Reference were taken and the estimated mean values and standard deviations (Step 1) are:

$$\hat{\mu}_R = -0.18, \hat{\mu}_T = -0.22, \hat{\sigma}_R^2 = 0.81, \hat{\sigma}_T^2 = 0.27.$$

In Step 2, the quantiles of the Reference product are calculated where the q -quantile of the standard normal distribution for $q = 0.1$ is given by $z_q = -1.28$ and the $(1 - q)$ -quantile is given by $z_{1-q} = 1.28$:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{R}_{0.1} &= \hat{\mu}_R + z_q \cdot \hat{\sigma}_R = -0.18 - 1.28 \cdot 0.9 = -1.33, \\ \hat{R}_{0.9} &= \hat{\mu}_R + z_{1-q} \cdot \hat{\sigma}_R = -0.18 + 1.28 \cdot 0.9 = 0.97. \end{aligned}$$

Then, in Step 3, the probability to observe a value of Test which is larger or smaller, respectively, than these quantiles is calculated. This is done by using the distribution function of a normally distributed random variable with the estimated parameters ($\hat{\mu}_T =$

$-0.22, \hat{\sigma}_T^2 = 0.27$) and comparing it to the estimated quantiles of the Reference product:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{C}_l &= P(X_{T,e} \leq \hat{R}_q) = P(X_{T,e} \leq -1.33) = 0.02, \\ \hat{C}_u &= P(X_{T,e} \geq \hat{R}_{1-q}) = 1 - P(X_{T,e} \leq 0.97) = 0.01.\end{aligned}$$

We also calculate the realization of the test statistic W :

$$w = 2q - (\hat{C}_l + \hat{C}_u) = 0.17.$$

164 The critical value is simulated with the provided Shiny-App or R-code and we obtain
165 $W(0.05, -0.1, 0.1, 20, 20) = 0.08$. We note that $W(0.05, -0.1, 0.1, 20, 20) < w$ and therefore
166 claim comparability.

167 **Approaches frequently used in practice for comparability claims**

168 In the following, we briefly introduce the statistical approaches which are currently used in
169 practice. We refer to [19] for a comprehensive overview of statistical approaches in quality
170 assessment. The approaches described in the following will be compared to the tail-test in
171 a simulation study.

172 **Tiered approach (Tsong et al., [4])**

Tsong et al. [4] advocate a tiered approach for the assessment of quality attributes: the quality attributes which are considered to be most critical are called Tier 1 attributes and should be assessed using a formal equivalence test for the mean value. Quality attributes which are less important are grouped as Tier 2 and are compared with so-called quality ranges and the least relevant quality attributes (Tier 3) are analyzed descriptively. The way the assessments are grouped into the tiers is a topic of debate and will not be considered in this paper; we refer to [20] for more on this. In this paper, we will only focus on Tier 1 and Tier 2 attributes. The statistical approaches discussed in this section are comparable to the FDA's approach in the withdrawn draft guidance [3]. The Tier 1 tests aims for a decision on

$$H_0 : |\mu_R - \mu_T| \geq \delta$$

against the alternative hypothesis

$$H_1 : |\mu_R - \mu_T| < \delta.$$

The equivalence margin δ is proposed to be $\delta = 1.5\sigma_R$. For a level α -test, it is suggested that a $(1 - 2\alpha)$ -confidence interval is calculated and equivalence is claimed if the confidence interval fully lies within the interval

$$[-1.5\sigma_R, 1.5\sigma_R].$$

173 In practice, the true standard deviation σ_R is not known and is therefore replaced by its
174 estimated value $\hat{\sigma}_R$. We refer to this test as *Tier 1-test* (T1-test) in the rest of the paper.

175

Quality ranges should be used for Tier 2 attributes [4]. For that, first a quality range is calculated:

$$[\hat{\mu}_R - X\hat{\sigma}_R, \hat{\mu}_R + X\hat{\sigma}_R],$$

176 where the factor X needs to be justified and discussed with the regulatory authority.
177 Commonly a value between 2 and 5 is used and some discussion on the choice of X is
178 provided in [21]. For claiming comparability, it is required that "a large proportion, say
179 90%, of the test results from the biosimilar lots [fall] within an acceptance range determined
180 by the reference product" [4]. We refer to this approach as the *quality range-approach* (qr-
181 approach) in this paper.

182 **Min/max approach**

The min/max approach is motivated by the idea that as all batches of Reference are already on the market, and therefore are obviously considered safe and efficacious, a batch of Test can be considered acceptable as long as it lies within the range of Reference. Therefore, only the most extreme values have to be compared. More formally, we define

$$\hat{t}_{\min} = \min_{i=1,\dots,n} x_i, \quad \hat{t}_{\max} = \max_{i=1,\dots,n} x_i,$$

and

$$\hat{r}_{\min} = \min_{i=1,\dots,m} y_i, \quad \hat{r}_{\max} = \max_{i=1,\dots,m} y_i.$$

183 If \hat{t}_{\min} is larger than \hat{r}_{\min} and \hat{t}_{\max} is smaller than \hat{r}_{\max} , then comparability has been
184 established with the *min/max approach* (mm-approach).

185 **Prediction interval in tolerance interval**

186 A combination of prediction and tolerance intervals was introduced by Boulanger [22] who
187 proposed basing the decision on comparability on the question as to whether future batches
188 of Test will lie within the range of Reference with a pre-specified level of confidence. There-
189 fore, this approach goes in the direction of a range-type hypothesis even though no explicit
190 hypotheses are stated. Boulanger [22] proposed defining the acceptable interval (the equiv-
191 alence margin) using a β -content γ -confidence tolerance interval [23] for Reference. For
192 making a decision if Test and Reference are comparable, a β -prediction interval is estimated
193 [24]. We will refer to this approach as the *prediction-interval-in-tolerance-interval-approach*
194 (piti-approach). We note that [9] also proposed an approach based on tolerance intervals.
195 However, their approach assumes a dependency structure between observations from the
196 same lot which is not compatible with our assumption of independent and identically dis-
197 tributed random variables.

198 **Set-up of the simulation study**

In the following section, we illustrate the operating characteristics of the tail-test compared
to the other introduced statistical approaches using our understanding of comparability,
i.e., we will simulate datasets under the above defined null (see Equation (1)) and alterna-
tive hypotheses and compare their rejection rates. We consider sample sizes relevant for
biosimilar development. For that, we assume an equal sample size of

$$n = m = 5, 10, 25, 100$$

199 observations for both Test and Reference. The motivation for the inclusion of one sample
200 size which is unrealistically high is to allow a check on the asymptotic (large sample size)
201 properties of the statistical methodologies: a reasonable statistical approach should reward
202 a large sample size and have the property that if the sample size increases, this should
203 make it more likely that the correct test decision is made.

204

205 We discuss four different scenarios for these sample sizes assuming independent and
206 identically normally distributed observations. The analyzed scenarios are comparable to
207 some of the scenarios analyzed by [22]. A graphical illustration of the scenarios is given in
208 Figure 3.

209 *Please place Figure 3 about here.*

- 210 1. Distributions of Test and Reference are identical (correct decision: comparable; $\mu_R =$
211 $\mu_T = 0$ and $\sigma_T = \sigma_R = 1$).
- 212 2. The mean values of Test and Reference are different and the variability of Test is
213 much smaller than that of Reference so that the distribution of Reference completely
214 covers the distribution of Test (correct decision: comparable; $\mu_R = 0$, $\mu_T = 0.9$,
215 $\sigma_R = 1$ and $\sigma_T = 0.4$).
- 216 3. The mean values of Test and Reference are identical, but the variability of Reference
217 is smaller than the variability of Test (correct decision: not comparable; $\mu_R = \mu_T = 0$
218 and $\sigma_R = 1$ and $\sigma_T = 2.15$).
- 219 4. The variances of Test and Reference are identical, but the distribution of Test is
220 shifted so that the situation is under Tsong's null hypothesis [4] (correct decision:
221 not comparable; $\mu_R = 0$ and $\mu_T = 1.5$ and $\sigma_R = \sigma_T = 1$).

222 Note that the judgements of the "correct decision" were made using our understanding
223 of comparability with $q = 0.05$ and an equivalence margin of $c = -0.34$, which corre-
224 sponds to the value of the test statistic W under Tsong's null hypothesis [4] ($\mu_R = 0$, $\mu_T =$
225 1.5 , $\sigma_R = \sigma_T = 1$). This setting is also used for deriving the critical value for the tail-test
226 in order to ensure comparability with the T1-test.

227

228 There exists selectable parameters (tuning parameters) in the qr-approach (X) and in
229 the piti-approach (β , γ) which allows us to calibrate the approaches for a specific value
230 of n and m such that the Type I error rate in Scenario 4 is controlled at $\alpha = 0.05$. Even
231 though, if applied in practice, one would use subject matter expertise or simulation studies
232 for choosing these tuning parameters, making the Type I error rates comparable to the

233 ones of the T1-test and the tail-test allows a meaningful comparison of the power profiles.
234 The mm-approach does not require tuning parameters by nature. However, we note that
235 the Type I error rate in Scenario 4 is roughly controlled by the nature of the methodology
236 for $m = n$. More details on the calibration of the approaches can be found in the online
237 supplement.

238

239 For all four described scenarios, 1000 datasets for Test and Reference were simulated and
240 the number of claims of comparability for all introduced statistical methods were recorded.
241 All simulations were performed with R 3.2.3 [18]. For the calculation of the tolerance
242 intervals, the R-package `tolerance` [25] was used.

243 Results

244 In Figure 4, we show the percentages of time in which comparability is claimed dependent
245 on the scenario for the four selected sample sizes. Scenario 4 is omitted since the compara-
246 bility of the rejection rates under Scenario 4 was enforced with the calibration (see above).
247 From the remaining scenarios, Scenarios 1 and 2 are the situations in which a claim of
248 comparability is desirable whereas Scenario 3 is a setting in which the products are not
249 truly comparable (low rate of comparability claims desirable).

250

251 We first consider the T1-test and note that the rate of comparability claims is among
252 the highest in Scenario 1 and is reasonably high also for small sample sizes. For example, for
253 $N = 10$, the rate of comparability claims is already higher than 80%. On the other hand,
254 the rate of comparability claims is very low in Scenario 2. This is expected since the focus
255 of the T1-test is on the mean value, but it is still a highly undesirable feature if a range-type
256 hypothesis is considered. Even more importantly, the rate of comparability claims is high
257 in Scenario 3 and the rate of comparability claims in this situation is increasing with an
258 increasing sample size and reaches 100% for $N = 100$. This illustrates that the T1-test
259 is not an appropriate approach if comparability is interpreted using a range-type hypothesis.

260

261 Next, we consider the mm-approach. This approach shows high rejection rates under

262 equal sample sizes if the variability of Test is much smaller than that of Reference (Scenario
263 2). Also, the patient's risk (false positive rate, Scenario 3) seems to be well-controlled.
264 However, if the distributions of Test and Reference are identical, the rate of comparability
265 claims is low (Scenario 1). This can be easily explained by calculating the expected rejection
266 rate: assuming that the maximum and minimum would be independent, there is a 50%
267 chance that the maximum of Test is smaller than the maximum of Reference and a 50%
268 that the minimum of Test is larger than the minimum of Reference leading to an expected
269 rejection rate of 25%. Since in fact the maximum and minimum are correlated, a slightly
270 lower rejection rate is expected and also observed in the presented simulation study. In
271 total, the mm-approach can only be recommended if the company is highly confident that
272 the variability of Test is much smaller than the variability of Reference.

273 *Please place Figure 4 about here.*

274 The performance of the piti-approach highly depends on the sample size: for $N = 5$,
275 the rate of comparability claims is more than 11% in Scenario 3 (not comparable is the
276 correct decision). Therefore, the rate of false positive decisions is too high for so small
277 sample sizes and the piti-approach cannot be recommended for $N = 5$. For $N = 10$, the
278 rate of comparability claims is already high in Scenario 1 and in Scenario 2 if compared
279 with other approaches. However, the rate of comparability claims is still only around 60%
280 which indicates that this is not a sufficient sample size in practice. The rate of compara-
281 bility claims does not reach 80% even for $N = 100$ in Scenario 1 indicating that increasing
282 the sample size does not greatly influence the power after a certain threshold is reached.
283 Therefore, this approach does not show reasonable asymptotic statistical properties. It
284 can only be recommended if only a very limited sample size ($n = m \approx 10$) is possible due
285 to practical reasons and one is willing to accept a low chance of success for that sample size.

286
287 The qr-approach behaves similar to the mm-approach for $N = 5$. With an increasing
288 sample size, the rate of comparability claims increases which is a highly desirable feature.
289 Nonetheless, the rate of comparability claims is in none of the discussed scenarios the high-
290 est of the compared approaches. The rate of comparability claims in Scenario 3 is low as

291 desirable.

292

293 For the tail-test, we note good control of the rate of false positive decisions in Scenarios
294 3. In Scenarios 1 and 2, we observe the desirable properties of an inferential methodol-
295 ogy: the probability of claiming comparability increases with an increasing sample size
296 and reaches 100% if $N = 100$ observations are included. In addition, the rate of compa-
297 rability claims is among the highest for all sample sizes in Scenario 2. Compared to the
298 mm-approach, a higher rate of comparability rates is also shown in Scenario 1 independent
299 of the sample size. The rate of comparability claims is also higher or similar for Scenario
300 1 compared to the qr-approach. Here, it should specifically be noted that for medium
301 sample sizes (e.g., $N = 25$), the rate of comparability claims is relevantly higher for the
302 tail-test than for the qr-approach (89% vs. 76%). Compared to the piti-approach, the rate
303 of comparability claims is lower for $N = 10$, but higher for $N = 25$. It is emphasized that
304 the rate of comparability claims for $N = 10$ is for all approaches so low that it is not a
305 sufficient sample size in practice. Therefore, in all situations in which the success rate is
306 reasonable, the tail-test outperforms all comparators.

307

308 For this simulation study, we calibrated the qr-approach, the piti-approach and the
309 tail-test by the use of tuning parameters or critical values (see the online supplement for
310 details) to ensure a similar rate of comparability claims in Scenario 4 for the different
311 sample sizes. This is a step which improved the comparability between the approaches.
312 While for the tail-test, it is obvious that the sample size needs to be taken into account in
313 the calculation of the critical values, this is not typically done for the two other approaches
314 when applied in practice. It is therefore important to emphasize that the sample size has a
315 major impact on the rate of comparability claims in Scenario 4. In Figure 5 we display the
316 relative change in percent of the tuning parameter or critical values which led to similar
317 rates of comparability claims (the parameter X for the qr-approach, the parameter β for
318 the piti-approach and the critical value for the tail-test) compared to the value of this
319 parameter for $N = 100$. For example, the value of X for $N = 5$ which leads to a rate
320 of comparability claims of 5% in Scenario 4 needs to be nearly twice the value which is

321 required for $N = 100$. If one would simply use the same value of X for $N = 5$ that is
322 used for $N = 100$, the rate of comparability claims increases from approximately 5% to
323 more than 30%. Most importantly, the qr-approach and the piti-approach reject for a fixed
324 parameter more often if a smaller sample size is used which might discourage companies
325 to use a reasonable sample size. This shows that also for an application in practice, the
326 planned number of observations needs to be taken into account during the decision making
327 process for the tuning parameters to ensure a low rate of comparability claims in scenarios
328 which one would not consider to be comparable.

329 *Please place Figure 5 about here.*

330 **Discussion**

331 Aligning the statistical methodology with the aim of the analysis is crucial from a scientific
332 point of view. Data analysis and statistical approaches can only give useful insights and
333 support drug development if the scientific questions are correctly transferred into the sta-
334 tistical framework. For an improved alignment, we propose a set of statistical hypotheses in
335 this paper which focus on comparing the ranges of Test and Reference instead of their mean
336 values for establishing comparability. The tail-test is, to the best of our knowledge, the
337 first proposal for an inferential statistical methodology for this class of hypotheses which
338 is applicable in the area of comparability claims. The properties of the tail-test were illus-
339 trated in the simulation study in comparison to several approaches which are frequently
340 used in practice for establishing comparability of quality attributes.

341
342 For the interpretation of the results of the simulation study, it is important to note
343 that some of the compared methods are not inferential in nature: for example, one may
344 interpret the min/max approach as a descriptive approach since the test decision is purely
345 based on the observed data only and the uncertainty of the estimation is not taken into
346 account. That is why one can argue that it is in principle not possible to draw any con-
347 clusions regarding the underlying distribution. Nonetheless, when these approaches are
348 applied in the context of a comparability assessment, a conclusion *is* made not only about

349 the few observations which were studied, but also about the process itself, i.e., the question
350 is answered if material produced with the analyzed manufacturing process (Test) will be
351 sufficiently comparable to Reference. That is why we assess the potential of all approaches,
352 inferential or descriptive by nature, in answering questions related to the underlying pop-
353 ulation, i.e., we assume that the approaches aim to answer an inferential question.

354

355 In summary, our analysis showed that the proposed tail-test has desirable operating
356 characteristics in a wide range of scenarios. In addition, we demonstrated that none of
357 the other approaches can be recommended for the assessment of quality attributes with-
358 out restrictions if a range-type hypothesis is used: the T1-test is not able to distinguish
359 between comparable and not comparable settings. The qr-approach had lower or similar
360 power than the tail-test in all situations. The rate of comparability claims for the piti-
361 approach does not reach 100% even if $N = 100$ observations for Test and Reference are
362 used and Test and Reference follow the same distribution. The piti-approach has therefore
363 no reasonable large sample properties. The mm-approach has an acceptable control of the
364 patient's risk. The developer's risk is only reasonably low if the variance of Test is much
365 smaller than that of Reference. In other cases, the rates of a comparability claim are low
366 – even if the distributions of Test and Reference are identical. Therefore, this approach is
367 only applicable if the biosimilar developer is highly confident that the variability of Test
368 will be lower than that of Reference, which can be a realistic scenario in biosimilar devel-
369 opment (see, for example, [8]). Due to the high dependence of the test result on individual
370 observations (no robustness), the application of the mm-approach requires a high level of
371 pre-specification of the analysis, e.g., the criteria for batch selection, the sample size and the
372 inclusion of all analyzed batches in the final analysis without the opportunity to select the
373 most favourable results. It should also be noted that an approximately equal sample size
374 of Test and Reference is required for the mm-approach for controlling the false positive rate.

375

376 It should be emphasized that there are also situations in which the tail-test is not
377 recommended without modifications: these are the situations in which the assumption of
378 independent and identical normally distributed observations is not justifiable. In these

379 situations, a carefully conducted simulation study to assess the operating characteristics of
380 potential approaches is required. It should, however, be emphasized that having represen-
381 tative data is relevant for all approaches, not only when an inferential approach is applied,
382 for which the representativeness of data is a formal requirement. Conclusions drawn with,
383 for example, a descriptive approach based on only a few, but highly auto-correlated, mea-
384 surements are also not a reasonable foundation for further steps in development. The
385 sample should in any case be representative of the manufacturing process in the sense that
386 the sample size is sufficient to capture the features of the underlying distributions. Other
387 situations in which our proposal is not applicable are the ones with such small sample sizes
388 such that the power of the proposed approach is too low. However, it should be emphasized
389 that none of the other methodologies showed reasonable performance for small sample sizes
390 over a wide range of scenarios.

391 **Conclusion**

392 The use of statistics in the comparability exercise of quality attributes is currently in the
393 focus of attention because both the EMA and the FDA are working on regulatory guid-
394 ances on this topic. In this paper, we proposed improving the alignment of the statistical
395 hypothesis testing with scientific judgment by shifting away from the often-used compari-
396 son of mean values towards a range-based comparison. The tail-test, our proposal for an
397 inferential methodology for this type of hypothesis, showed favorable performance over a
398 wide range of scenarios in a simulation study. In addition, we demonstrated that statis-
399 tical approaches which are currently used in practice all have serious weaknesses for the
400 assessment of comparability if a range-based hypothesis is considered.

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